

Parent–Child Relationship and Deviant Behavior of Juvenile Children: the Mediating Role of Domestic Violence Exposure: Basis for A Proposed Intervention Scheme

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Abstract: *Parents' negligence may produce rebellious children that almost always became a menace to the society by becoming deviants. This study focuses on the mediating role of domestic violence exposure on the relationship between parent-child relationship and deviant behavior of juvenile children. Questionnaires were distributed among 350 parents as respondents of the study, wherein the data gathered were treated utilizing statistical tools such as Mean, Pearson r, Medgraph, and Regressions. The result of the study are as follows: The level of parent-child relationship was very high; the level of deviant behavior of juvenile children was low; the level of domestic violence exposure was low; there was significant relationship between parent-child relationship and domestic violence exposure; there was a significant relationship between domestic violence exposure and deviant behavior of juvenile children; there was significant relationship between parent-child relationship and deviant behavior of juvenile children; there was partial mediation of domestic violence exposure on the relationship between parent-child relationship and deviant behavior of juvenile children. The implication of the study concerns about the morality foundation of every family, wherein convictions must not only lies on the existing law of the land but on their spiritual belief as well, particularly in determining what is right and what is wrong.*

Keywords: *Parent-Child Relationship, Deviant Behavior, Juvenile Children, Mediating Role, Domestic Violence Exposure, Proposed Intervention Scheme*

I. Introduction

Many minors today violate social norms and expectations because of their awareness of the prevailing law, wherein minor offenders are not liable to the crimes they have committed. Deviance can be something as small as dressing in vulgar clothing, or something as serious as burning someone's house down (Daruwalla et al., 2017). Regretfully there are minors today who commits formal deviant acts such as robbery, rape and murder, which are punishable by the law for those who are in their legal age. There also those who commit informal deviant acts not punishable by revised penal code, but are considered lewd acts unacceptable to the society, such as pissing in public places (Kramar, 2011).

Consequently, deviant behavior is connected to different upgrading patterns. Negative upgrading pattern is characterized by neglectful behavior from the parent, and the child receives little direction or support. A high degree of demandingness is given by the parent, but little support is offered in positive upgrading. The upgrading pattern is

conducive to the most positive results. In particular, if one would attempt to prevent delinquency among children, then a focus on high levels of support and demandingness would be appropriate. High levels of emotional support and parental involvement would also be stressed; thus, upgrading patterns affect greatly the delinquent behavior among children (Nassar et al., 2015).

Similarly, children who are rejected by their parents, who grow up in homes with considerable conflict, or who are inadequately supervised are at the greatest risk of becoming delinquent. Adolescence is a time of expanding vulnerabilities and opportunities that accompany the widening social and geographic exposure to life beyond school or family. Concerns on the rising of delinquency cases due to the development of delinquent behavior among youth should become the priority among all the related parties nowadays (Sharma, 2012). The psychosocial outcomes of children exposed to domestic violence had significantly worse outcomes compared to those who had not experienced any form of domestic violence. The impact of witnessing domestic violence can vary for all individuals and may have many developmental impacts on children, and those can start as early as conception and carry on through adulthood depending on the severity of the trauma (Curran, 2013).

II. Literature Review

Few study were conducted tackling the present study, wherein most cases are only concentrating on topics such as parent-child relationship and juvenile delinquency, which the latter is actually tantamount to deviant acts of children; however, no study touches yet concerning parent-child relationship strained by domestic violence exposure and its indirect relationship to deviant behavior of juvenile children. The study was relevant in providing corrective seminars to the parents regarding violence inside their homes, which would lessen the incidence of juvenile delinquency later.

It was found out that adolescence is the transition of children into the adult stage physical or physiological changes cause young parents in the parent-child interactive communication of distress; young children in the psychological changes (such as: interest on the popular thing, need friends with same age, eager to independence, against the authority of the opposite sex interested in seeking self-image, etc.), the same, a damaged parent-child relationship makes young people having difficulty adapting to their parents resulting often to deviant behavior or juvenile delinquency. Complex causes include physical, psychological factors, family factors, school factors, social factors and diversity into account; including family structure and family relationships interact with youth of deviant behavior (Qiang, 2012).

Similarly, a study found out that even if the children have close ties with their parents, exposure to domestic violence is distressing to them and is associated with a host of mental health symptoms both in childhood and in later life. The best documented mental health effects include symptoms of posttraumatic stress, depression, and anxiety. Exposure to serious domestic violence as a child is also associated with offending as an adult. Among a sample of domestic violence offenders, those who had as a child seen a parent use a weapon were more likely to commit an offense involving a weapon as an adult (Murrell et al., 2005)

A recent study assessing the effects of children's exposure to violence may be fraught with methodological problems, and urge caution in drawing cause and effect assumptions regarding children's exposure, wherein majority was also found out to display deviant behavior (Chan & Yeung, 2009). Also, the study assessing children's exposure to domestic violence, particularly between parents based on unique populations of children drawn from refugee shelters, representing the most recently and severely affected population showed children to become deviant children in conflict with the law violating existing policies as well as rules and regulation within the camp (DeBoard-Lucas, & Grych, 2011).

In addition, it is also important to note that children's exposure to domestic and family violence occurs within what DeBoard-Lucas and Grych called a constellation of risk and disadvantage. That is, domestic and family violence often occurs alongside a host of other risk factors, such as parental substance abuse, poverty, family dysfunction, other forms of child abuse and neglect, mental ill health and social isolation (Bromfield et al., 2010).

Another research study disclosed as well that presence of multiple stressors in a child's life elevate the risk of negative outcomes and render indistinct the exact relationship between domestic violence and those negative outcomes, such as anti-social behavior and violation of the existing law (Goddard & Bedi, 2010).

Delinquent activity or deviant behavior is a broad term that captures a multitude of activities. Many deviant behaviors by minors do not lead to arrests, and self-reports of deviant activity are a function of memory and willingness to disclose information. Thus, deviant behavior appears to have two contexts in which it can be measured: from law enforcement and from self-report. While using arrest records of juvenile delinquents is an effective way to map responses to deviant behavior from law enforcement, self-reports of delinquent behavior are a more effective way to estimate day to day delinquent activities of an individual. Early research revealed two important deviant behavior trajectories individuals may follow: childhood persistent and adolescent-onset. Childhood onset deviant behavior tends to have an early presence of harsh parenting and disruptive behaviors and temperaments compared to adolescent onsets. Interestingly, sex differences are almost non-existent in childhood persistent compared to adolescent onset where boys display much higher rates.

Family violence is a broader term encapsulating violence between family members as well as intimate partners. Family violence is the preferred term in Indigenous populations as it better captures the kinship and extended family relationships in Indigenous communities. Domestic violence includes physical, sexual, emotional and psychological abuse; it best reflects the types of violence children are directly and indirectly exposed to in the home. Furthermore, children's exposure to domestic and family violence has become a prominent policy issue comparatively recently. In the past two decades, mounting evidence about the extent to which children are exposed to domestic and family violence and the effect this has on their development has created impetus for policy responses to this issue. The above-cited literatures provided a vivid paradigm of the study based on comparison and contrast; it aided the researchers in determining the mediating effect of parent attachment on the relationship between child exposure to domestic violence and deviant acts.

The study is anchored to attachment theory developed by Bowlby (1969/1982). He postulated that attachment is an emotional bond; this bond comprises comfort, safety, and support to an individual. In the past few decades, John Bowlby's attachment theory has greatly enriched people's understanding of social development during infancy and early childhood. More recently, attachment theory has provided a theoretical basis for understanding the presence of emotional and behavioral problems during adolescence (Marsh et al., 2003). Therefore, attachments can be seen as an important construct in understanding future development and behavioral patterns of individuals.

The study also anchored to Travis Hirschi's social bond theory (1969). It is one of the most frequently investigated frameworks for the parent-child relationship and delinquency or deviant behavior (Vold et al., 2002). Hirschi's (1969) theory mentions that human beings are not innately programmed to conform to social norms or rules, but are rather guided by primitive instincts and hence naturally capable for committing criminal acts. One of Hirschi's fundamental propositions is that there is an inverse relationship between social bonds and delinquency (Hirschi, 1969). It assumes that delinquent behaviors occur when the individual's bond to family and society is weak or broken.

The study is anchored as well to Social Learning Theory theorized by Bandura (1977). It posits that people learn from one another, via observation, imitation, and modeling. The theory has often been called a bridge between behaviorist and cognitive learning theories because it encompasses attention, memory, and motivation. Social Learning Theory is the school of behavioral thought that looks at both the internal and external thought processes (Robbins et al., 2012). Through social learning theory, it can be seen the importance of modeling and communication (verbal and non-verbal) for children and their developmental growth. Through much research and experimentation, it was determined that children often will model the behaviors of those around them. In a famous study by Albert Bandura, he studied children at the Stanford University Nursery School using a doll named "Bobo". During this study, children watched researchers acting aggressively towards the doll then, when children were left alone with the doll, they modeled that behavior and extended that aggression towards other toys (Cooper & Lesser,

2015). Children exposed to violence regardless of their positive parent-child relationship tend to adopt violence when they are growing up.

Other theories such as those of Moffitt (1993) and Patterson (Patterson & Yoerger, 2002) go beyond explaining only level differences in deviant behavior and examine how deviant behavior changes by age and often influenced by the exposure of children to violence during their younger years inside their homes. The child's deviant behavior affects parents' disciplinary strategies, resulting in harsher and inconsistent punishments and less involvement by parents in the socialization process (Patterson, 1982). These negative child-parent transactions increase the risk of setting a child off on a delinquent path that starts in the early teens, entails many delinquent acts and persists far into adulthood (Moffitt 1993; Patterson & Yoerger 2002)

Presented in Figure 1 is the conceptual framework of the study consisting of the three variables as follows: The independent variable is *parent-child relationship* (Dixon et al., 2014) with indicators *doing together, communication/attention, helping/understanding behaviors and feelings, love/respect, and conflict*. Doing together are the activities and chores both parents and child are working in tandem, communication/attention refers to the conversation between the parents and child as well as interacting non-verbally, helping/understanding behaviors and feelings means both parties are showing mutual kindness, love/respect refers to the filial love existing that can be express in caring for each other, and conflict, the area where parent and children argue and disagree on certain things. The dependent variable is *deviant behavior* (Sanchez et al., 2016) with indicators *minor infraction and serious infraction*. Minor infractions are those that are commonly handled by teachers in a classroom. Serious infraction means a violation of a facility rule that imposes a serious risk, which can be considered a conflict with the law.

The mediating variable is *domestic violence exposure* (Sajadi et al., 2014) with indicators *exposure to parental conflicts, exposure to the father's violence against the mother, child's involvement in parents' violence, family risk factors, exposure to violence at school or in the community, exposure to violence through violent video technologies, and adult violence against the child*. Exposure to parental conflicts refers to the verbal confrontation between husband and wife in front of the children, exposure to the father's violence against the mother refers to the physical violence of the husband to his wife with the child witnessing the scene, child's involvement in parents' violence refers to the inclusion of the child in the physical violence; family risk factors refers to the exposure of children to substance use of parents, exposure to violence at school or in the community means the child witnessing the physical beating of other

The main thrust of the study was to determine the mediating role of parent-child relationship and deviant behavior of juvenile children. The first research objective is to determine the level of parent-child relationship in terms of doing together; communication/attention; helping/understanding behaviors and feelings; love/respect; and, conflict. The second objective is to determine the level of deviant behavior of juvenile children in terms of minor infraction and serious infraction. Thirdly, determine the level of domestic violence exposure in terms of exposure to parental conflicts; exposure to the father's violence against the mother; child's involvement in parents' violence; family risk factors; exposure to violence at school or in the community; exposure to violence through violent video technologies; and, adult violence against the child.

The fourth research objective is to determine the significant relationship between in terms of parent-child relationship and deviant behavior of juvenile children parent-child relationship and domestic violence exposure; and, deviant behavior of juvenile children and domestic violence exposure. The fifth is to determine the significance of mediation of parent attachment on the relationship between child exposure to domestic violence and deviant acts. Lastly, to propose an intervention scheme based on the findings of the study.

Furthermore, these are the null hypotheses of the study. There is no significant relationship between; parent-child relationship and deviant behavior of juvenile children; parent-child relationship and domestic violence exposure; and, deviant behavior of juvenile children and domestic violence exposure. There is no significance of mediation of parent attachment on the relationship between child exposure to domestic violence and deviant acts.

The findings of the study would benefit the families globally, considering that they have the vital role in shaping the characters of their children regardless of race and nationality. Globally, every nation should see to it that the basic unit of the society which is the family would have a strong foundation and parents should be taught by the state how to take care of their children with positive value system. Family associations to growing youngsters are directly proportional with the behavior outcomes. Deeper and well-established family relations decrease the chances of negative behavioral leanings in adolescents.

For a child, parents and family, make major of its social life especially at the early developing years of age. There may be many reasons for an adolescent to show antisocial behavior, but it matters that how parents and family react at that point. Children's and adolescents' interactions and relationships with family and peers influence the development of antisocial behavior and delinquency. Family interactions are most important during early childhood, but they can have long-lasting effects. In early adolescence, relationships with peers take on greater importance. It should be no surprise, therefore, when families have difficulties with the task laid on them, that the product often is juvenile delinquency. Family structure (who lives in a household) and family functioning (how the family members treat one another) are two general categories under which family effect on delinquency. Children reared by affectionate, consistent parents are unlikely to commit serious crimes either as juveniles or as adults.

Furthermore, the study would benefit the Department of Social Welfare and Development by learning the extent of parent's attachment on the development of deviant acts among the children due to exposure to violence and formulate counseling and campaign awareness materials, which they can use in the rehabilitation of juvenile delinquents and the latter use in educating parents in every barangays to be discreet when arguing and quarreling so as not to leave confusion among their children. Law enforcers would also benefit from the result of the study by doing their part in the information campaign emphasizing RA 9262, wherein the rights of women and children are protected by the law to avoid further damage to the emotional and psychological elements of the children. Parents would also benefit by learning the effect of their bickering inside their homes that affects the children psychologically, and may agree to argue their misunderstanding outside the sight and hearings of the children. Future researchers on the other hand would benefit by utilizing this study as a premise in pursuing another study particularly factors influencing the deviant acts of adolescents.

III. Material and Methods

Presented in this section are the methods that were used in the study such as study research subject, instruments, as well as design, and procedure.

IV. Research Respondents

There were 350 parents taken as respondents of the study. To avoid responses based on speculations, the study employed the convenience sampling technique in determining the sampling population; the respondents culled from the list provided by Women's and Children's Desk among the Police Stations located in Police Regional Office 10, wherein children in conflict with the law endorsed to the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD-R 10) were recorded in the police blotter. Their parents were traced by the researcher and take them as respondents of the study.

The criteria of choosing the respondents include the fact that they are parents of deviant children whose behaviors conflict with the law, and they are residents of Northern Mindanao. Parents whose children were not rescued by the law enforcers were excluded in the study; while those who were approached and agreed but declined later on were classified as withdrawing respondents. The study was conducted during the 2nd Semester of School Year 2019-2020.

V. Materials and Instrument

An adapted questionnaire was the instrument that was used in the study, consolidated by the researcher from the studies of Dixson et al. (2014), Sajadi et al. (2014), and Sanches et al. (2016). The preliminary draft was forwarded to the research adviser for possible comments and suggestions; afterwards, it was submitted to the panel of experts to check whether it's reliable and valid. It was also pilot tested by taking 40 respondents and compute it through Cronbach Alpha yielding a Cronbach Value of .871 , .901 and .756. The questionnaire tackled the assessment of parent-child relationship and deviant behavior of juvenile children with domestic violence exposure as mediating variable.

The independent variable is parent-child relationship with four indicators as follows: Doing together, communication/attention, helping/understanding behaviors and feelings, love/respect, and conflict (Sanches et al., 2016). The dependent variable is deviant behavior of juvenile children with indicators minor infraction and serious infraction (Sajadi et al., 2014). Domestic violence exposure is the mediating variable with seven indicators as follows: Exposure to parental conflicts, exposure to the father's violence against the mother, child's involvement in parents' violence, family risk factors, exposure to violence at school or in the community, exposure to violence through the use of violent video technologies; and, adult violence against the child (Dixson et al., 2014).

The five gradations of variables with a range of means, descriptions, and interpretations are as follows: a range the mean of 4.20-5.00 would mean Very High which translates that the item is always evident; 3.40-4.19 would mean High which translates that the item is often evident; 2.60-3.39 would mean Moderate which translates that the item is sometimes evident; 1.80-2.59 would mean Low which translates that the item is seldom evident, and lastly, 1.00-1.79 Very Low which translates that the item is never evident.

VI. Design and Procedure

The study utilized the quantitative, non-experimental design using correlation technique. This method allows data analysis from many subjects simultaneously. Moreover, correlation analysis can study a wide range of variables and their interrelations. On the negative side, findings of correlation do not indicate causations such as cause and effect relationships (Dudovskiy, 2018). It is a method of statistical evaluation used to study the strength of a relationship between two, numerically measured, continuous variables. This particular type of analysis is useful when a researcher wants to establish if there are possible connections between variables. It is often misunderstood that correlation analysis determines cause and effect; however, this is not the case because other variables that are not present in the research may have impacted on the results (Allen, 2017).

In matter of direct and direct path analysis, there is no more vivid explanation that what Pajares and Miller (1994) elaborated; they mentioned about the two types of effects of path model. The first is the direct effect, and the second is the indirect effect. When the independent variable has an arrow directed towards the dependent variable, then it is said to be the direct effect. When an independent variable has an effect on the dependent variable, through the other variable, then it is said to be an indirect effect. To see the total effect of the independent variable, it is necessary to add the direct and indirect effect. One variable may not have a direct effect, but it may have an indirect effect as well. Path analyses were appropriate in determining the mediating role of domestic violence exposure on the relationship between parent-child relationship and deviant behavior of juvenile children.

Questionnaires was forwarded to respective Chiefs of Police/Station Commanders of the respective City/Municipal Police Stations in Police Regional Office 10 (PRO 10), Camp Alagar, Lapasan, Cagayan de Oro City and the Regional Office of DSWD , Regional Office X, after Regional Director, Police Regional Office 10 and DSWD (R-X) approved the letter requesting to secure the list of the parents of children rescued for deviant acts, which was traced by the researcher to conduct a survey. The questionnaire scrutinized by the research adviser with comments and suggestions, which later on submitted to the panel of expert for reliability and validity was utilized after the approval of the respective Chiefs of Police/ Station Commanders to release the list of the parents of rescued children in the Women and Children Desk blotter records.

Thus, the questionnaires were distributed among the respondents explaining at the same time the purpose of the research study and its relevance to the society in general. After the respondents have finished answering the questionnaires, the researcher collected all the answered questionnaires and the valid ones were treated accordingly. The collected data were subjected to statistical computation, tabulation, analysis and interpretation and were presented in the succeeding chapters.

For more comprehensive analysis and interpretation of the gathered data, the following statistical treatments were used. The researcher analyzed the data gathered with the following statistical tools: Mean was used to determine the level of parent-child relationship, deviant behavior and exposure to domestic violence. Correlation Analysis was applied to quantitatively determine the relationship between parent-child relationship and domestic violence exposure; domestic violence exposure and deviant behavior; and, parent-child relationship and deviant behavior. Medgraph utilizing Sobel z-test was also used to determine if domestic violence exposure mediates on the relationship between parent-child relationship and deviant behavior. The Sobel z-test was utilized in testing the significance of the mediation. Regression was utilized as input to mediation test, whether parent-child relationship influences domestic violence exposure and parent-child relationship influences deviant behavior. Mediation Test Technique is a universal application and widely accepted technique as a valuable and authentic tool to assess mediation effects of variables.

The procedure was utilized to determine the mediating effect of parent attachment on the relationship between child exposure to violence and deviant acts. This includes the computation of the three regression equations: First, the regression of the mediator child exposure to violence towards parent attachment as the independent variable; second, the regression of the dependent variable, which is deviant acts; and, third, the regression of deviant acts as the dependent variable on both child exposure to violence as the independent variable and on parent attachment as the mediator. For the mediation to hold: In the first regression equation, the independent variable must affect the mediator. In the second regression equation, the independent variable must affect the dependent variable. In the final regression, the mediator must affect the dependent variable even to the exclusion of the independent variable.

The researcher monitored, ensured, and adhered to all ethical requirements in conducting the study. Prior to the actual giving of the questionnaires to various police offices, the research proponent submitted the data instrument to the UMERC for review and approval and adhered to the study requirements and protocol assessments and validated/standardized criteria, particularly in managing the size of the actual population and the data being considered because the study requires human participation. The UMERC granted a Certificate of Approval (Appendix G) with Protocol Number UMERC-2021- 037/February 19, 2021. Therefore, the researcher ensured that police officers who participated in the study were invited, and consent was placed. It is a crucial mechanism for ensuring that individuals are shown professional conduct by offering conscientious consent for a voluntary act.

VII. Results and Discussion

This section exhibited the result and discussion of the study. The order of presentation follows that of the study objectives.

Level of Parent-Child Relationship

Table 1 displays the level of parent-child relationship with the mean scores of indicators ranging from 3.91 to 4.73 with an overall mean score of 4.32 described as very high level. The standard deviation of 0.438 indicated clustered responses from the respondents considering the fact that it did not exceed 1.0.

The indicator with the highest mean score is *Love/Respect* garnering a mean score of 4.73 described as very high level with a standard deviation of 0.449 indicating clustered responses, which means that love and respect is

very evident in the parent-child relationship. In terms of *Communication/Attention* with the mean score of 4.50 labeled as very high level and a standard deviation of 0.455 showing clustered responses; this indicates that communication/attention is very evident in the parent-

Table 1
Level of Parent-Child Relationship

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Doing Together	0.763	3.91	High
Communication/Attention	0.455	4.50	Very High
Helping/Understanding Behavior and Feelings	0.541	4.08	High
Love/Respect	0.449	4.73	Very High
Conflict	0.674	4.39	Very High
Overall	0.438	4.32	Very High

child relationship. When it comes to the indicator *Conflict*, the garnered mean score is 4.39 declared as very high level having a standard deviation of 0.674 manifesting clustered responses. This signifies that conflict is very evident in the parent-child relationship. In terms of *Helping/Understanding Behavior and Feelings*, the mean score is 4.08 labeled as high level with a standard deviation of 0.541 indicating clustered responses. This means that helping/understanding behavior and feelings is evident in the parent-child relationship. Last but not the least is the indicator *Doing Together* garnering a mean score of 3.91 labeled as high level with the standard deviation of 0.763 showing clustered responses. This disclosed that doing together is evident in the parent-child relationship.

The level of parent-child relationship was very high. This means that the relation between parent and child was very evident. The indicator *Love/Respect* is labeled very high, which means that it is very evident in the parent-child relationship. Parents declared that they were showing unconditional love to their children, encouraging their child to show respect to parents and to others as well as being truthful to their children. This means that parents set a good example to their children when it comes to love and respect. The result supports the statement of Kuppens et al. (2009) who stated that early experiences of care, and the attachment relationship with the parents, have a long-lasting impact on the child that strengthen the bond, love and respect as the child grow older.

In terms of *Communication/Attention*, it was labeled as very high level, which means that communication/attention was very evident in the parent-child relationship, particularly in the area of instilling to the children to obey parents, teaching them how to do things right, and instilling to the children to be good always. This way children will learn to be obedient while at the same time recognizing what is right and what is wrong. The finding coincides with the statement of Fearon et al. (2010) who elucidated that parent-child attachment is described as an outline of emotional and behavioral communication that develops over time, particularly, in contexts where children express a need for attention, calm, support or safety.

When it comes to the indicator *Conflict*, it was described as very high level. This means that conflict was very evident in the parent-child relationship. Conflict emanates from parents' perspectives such as making sure my child understands my view on something that concerns him/her, encouraging my child to express his/her opinion of something, and being open to my child's suggestions or views. This shows that respecting each other's opinion is

part of relationship but still the right thing to do would prevail. The result conformed the statement of Klahr et al. (2011) emphasizing that parent–child conflict is comprised of mutual negative behaviors of both the parent and child but toleration may ease the tension.

Helping/Understanding Behavior and Feelings as one of the indicators is rated high level, which means that it was evident in the parent-child relationship best expressed through understanding child’s situation, teaching the child to do hard works (cleaning, cooking, yard-work), and showing compassion to the child whenever he/she commits mistake. Thus, bringing up a child with understanding and at the same time helping them do things right would make them responsible adults. The outcome is in accordance with the concept of Fearon et al. (2010) who emphasized that parents’ capability to perceive, understand and react promptly to their child’s needs and attention, in turn influence the quality of their attachment bonds.

The indicator *Doing Together* was rated high level, which was evident as part of parent-child relationship. It is best described through the parents’ conformation that they are playing together with their child, eating together with my child, and buying my child things. This means that the physical presence of the parents to their children and doing things together will strengthen their bond and love. The finding coincides with the statement of Walters (2018) who accentuated that children who actively seek proximity with their parents on reunion and communicate their distress are securely attached.

Level of Deviant Behavior of Juvenile Children

Table 2 presents the level of deviant behavior of juvenile children with an overall mean score of 1.93 declared as low and having a standard deviation of 0.902 indicating clustered responses form the respondents. This shows that the deviant behavior of juvenile children is less evident. In terms of *Minor Infraction*, the garnered mean score is 2.12 or low level with the standard deviation of 0.973 indicating clustered responses.

Table 2
Level of Deviant Behavior of Juvenile Children

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Minor Infraction	0.973	2.12	Low
Serious Infraction	0.943	1.74	Very Low
Overall	0.902	1.93	Low

This means that minor infraction is less evident among juvenile children. The indicator *Serious Infraction* garnered a mean score of 1.74 labeled as very low level with a standard deviation of 0.943 manifesting clustered responses. This shows that serious infraction is not evident among juvenile children.

The level of deviant behavior of juvenile children was low, which shows that the deviant behavior of juvenile children was less evident. In terms of *Minor Infraction*, it was rated as low level, which means that minor infraction as part of the behavior of juvenile children was less evident. Minor infractions that seldom committed includes having lied to adults, particularly family members, teachers, and etc.; also, having skipped classes because he/she didn’t feel like going but rather wants to stay with colleagues, or to go for a ride instead; and, having been to school or to class after drinking alcohol. The result supports the statement of Kassim (2016) who stressed that many

of the juvenile offences are related to drug abuse and excessive alcohol use. The rise in social deviance among adolescents can be viewed from various aspects and often are minor infractions.

The indicator *Serious Infraction* was labeled as very low level, which shows that serious infraction is not evident among juvenile children. This means that juvenile delinquents in Bukidnon area are not involve in serious infractions. The result coincides with the statement of Sherman (2006) who stated that by simply looking at national percentages of criminal behavior by minors may not accurately represent the nature of delinquency in the country, in most cases, isolated ones happened.

Level of Domestic Violence Exposure

Table 3 shows the level of domestic violence exposure with mean scores ranging from 1.22 to 2.99 and an overall mean score of 1.97 described as low level

Table 3
Level of Domestic Violence Exposure

Items	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
We (spouses) are disagreeing with each other	1.114	2.41	Low
We (spouses) are hurting each other's feelings	1.006	2.16	Low
We (spouses) are arguing with each other over our child	1.101	2.22	Low
Having seen us (parents) stopped one another from doing something	0.960	1.84	Low
Having seen us (parents) arguing over meals	1.060	1.95	Low
Having seen us (parents) broke or destroyed something on purpose	0.921	1.64	Very Low
Having seen us (parents) hurting one another physically	1.017	1.74	Very Low
Having seen us (parents) threatened one another holding sharp or killing tools when in conflict	0.834	1.55	Very Low
Having seen us (parents) using sharp or killing tools hurting one another	0.829	1.44	Very Low
Having yelled at us (spouses) when we fight	1.028	1.85	Low
Having ask somebody else to help her/him in stopping us (spouses)	0.996	1.57	Very Low
Having been physically engaged in our (spouses) fighting	0.743	1.30	Very Low
Being used to see us (spouses) hurt one another	0.766	1.52	Very Low
Having tried to escape from where we (spouses) are fighting	0.880	1.41	Very Low
Having served as mediator between us (spouses)	0.889	1.44	Very Low
Is worried that we (parents) are using substance	1.242	1.87	Low
Being worried that the member of the household are using substance	1.291	2.03	Low
Being disturbed of the happenings inside our house	1.298	2.08	Low
Having heard someone in the neighborhood or the school selling or in conflict with another person	1.319	2.64	Moderate
Having been annoyed someone in the neighborhood or the school	1.379	2.48	Low

annoyed the child by making fun of him/her or calling him/her name			
Having been hurt by someone physically, by hitting, kicking, or similar activities	1.290	2.43	Low
Having seen someone get hurt in the neighborhood or the school	1.262	2.44	Low
Having been hurt by others in the neighborhood or the school emotionally or psychology	1.278	2.31	Low
Having seen scenes in TV or movies that someone got hurt or was killed	1.375	2.99	Moderate
Having seen in a visual game (like PlayStation) that someone got hurt or was killed	1.396	2.89	Moderate
Having played violent video games online	1.373	2.65	Moderate
Having been violated by an adult in the family	1.077	1.55	Very Low
Having been hurt by a family member physically	1.201	2.17	Very Low
Having been an immoral relationship with another person outside the family	0.711	1.24	Very Low
Having been an immoral relationship with another family member	0.673	1.22	Very Low
Overall	0.708	1.97	Low

having a standard deviation of 0.798 manifesting clustered responses from the respondents. This means that the domestic violence exposure of juveniles is less evident. The statement with the highest mean score is *Having seen scenes in TV or movies that someone got hurt or was killed*, with the mean score of 2.99 labeled as moderate level with the standard deviation of 1.375 indicating spread out responses from the respondents considering that it exceeds 1.0. The statement with the second highest mean score is *Having seen in a visual game (like PlayStation) that someone got hurt or was killed* with the mean score of 2.89 described as moderate with the standard deviation of 1.396 manifesting spread out responses.

The statement with the third highest mean score is *Having played violent video games online* with the mean score of 2.65 labeled as moderate level with the standard deviation of 1.373 disclosing spread out responses. This means that it is moderately evident that the juvenile children are exposed to violence in TV, visual games and video games.

The level of domestic violence exposure was described as low level, which means that the domestic violence exposure of juveniles is less evident. This implies that domestic violence is a rare occurrence. Although low, the usual incidents that sometimes happened includes children watched scenes in TV or movies that someone got hurt or was killed, and played violent video games online. Children only saw violence in the monitor but not in actual incidents. The result is in accordance with the statement of Carroll-Lind et al. (2011) who elaborated that the nature of children's exposure to domestic and family violence is manifold, ranging from witnessing (including seeing and overhearing violence and witnessing its effects on televisions and other platforms) to being directly involved.

Significance of the Relationship between Parent-Child Relationship and Domestic Violence Exposure

Table 4 manifested the significance of the relationship between parent-child relationship and domestic violence exposure. The result showed that all the indicators of parent-child relationship is significantly correlated with the mediating variable domestic violence exposure disclosed as follows: Doing together ($p\text{-value}=0.000<0.05$),

communication/attention (p-value=0.000<0.05), helping/understanding behavior and feelings (p-value=0.000<0.05), love/respect (p-value=0.007<0.05), Conflict (p-value=0.011<0.05).

Table 4
Significance of the Relationship between Parent-Child Relationship and Domestic Violence Exposure

Parent-Child Relationship	Domestic Violence Exposure
	Overall
Doing Together	-.453* (0.000)
Communication/Attention	-.260* (0.000)
Helping/Understanding Behavior and Feelings	-.288* (0.000)
Love/Respect	-.148* (0.007)
Conflict	-.141* (0.011)
Overall	-.357* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

Overall computation showed an r-value of -.357 and a p-value of 0.000, which is lesser when compared to the level of significance of 0.05 indicating significant relationship thereby rejecting the null hypothesis. It could be declared therefore that there is a significance of the relationship between parent-child relationship and domestic violence exposure.

There was significant relationship between parent-child relationship and domestic violence exposure. The result showed that all the indicators of parent-child relationship is significantly correlated with the mediating variable domestic violence exposure. It could be declared therefore that correlation existed between parent-child relationship and domestic violence exposure. The outcome supports the study of Murrell et al. (2005), who found out that even if the children have close ties with their parents, exposure to domestic violence is distressing to them and is associated with a host of mental health symptoms both in childhood and in later life.

Significance of the Relationship between the Domestic Violence Exposure and Deviant Behavior of Juvenile Children

C 5 displays the significance of the relationship between the domestic violence exposure and deviant behavior of juvenile children. The result disclosed that the mediating variable domestic violence exposure is correlated with the indicators of deviant behavior of juvenile children as follows: Minor infraction (p-value=0.000<0.05) and serious infraction (p-value=0.000<0.05).

The overall computation showed an r-value of .777 and the p-value of 0.000 is greater than 0.05 level of significance indicating significant relationship and the

Table 5
Significance of the Relationship between the Domestic Violence Exposure and Deviant Behavior of Juvenile Children

Domestic Violence Exposure	Deviant Behavior of Juvenile Children		
	Minor Infraction	Serious Infraction	Overall
Overall	.756* (0.000)	.706* (0.000)	.777* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level. *

rejection of the null hypothesis. It is therefore safe to say that there is a significant relationship between domestic violence exposure and deviant behavior of juvenile children.

There was significant relationship between parent-child relationship and deviant behavior of juvenile children. Result shows that all the indicators of parent-child relationship were correlated with all the indicators of deviant behavior of juvenile children except between conflict and minor. However, it still can be declared that there was significant relationship between parent-child relationship and deviant behavior of juvenile children. The finding confirmed the study of Qiang (2012), who found out that a damaged parent-child relationship makes young people having difficulty adapting to their parents resulting often to deviant behavior or juvenile delinquency.

Significance of the Relationship between the Parent-Child Relationship and Deviant Behavior of Juvenile Children

Table 6 manifested the significance of the relationship between significance of the relationship between the parent-child relationship and deviant behavior of juvenile children. Result shows that all the indicators of parent-child relationship is correlated with all the indicators deviant behavior of juvenile children except between conflict and minor infraction (p-value=0.071>0.05) indicating no significant relationship. Correlation between indicators are shown as follows: Between doing together and minor infraction (p-value=0.000<0.05); between doing together and serious infraction (p-value=0.000<0.05); between communication/attention and minor infraction (p-value=0.000<0.05); between communication/attention and serious infraction (p-value=0.000<0.05); between helping/understanding behavior and feelings and minor infraction (p-value=0.000<0.05); between helping/understanding behavior and feelings and serious infraction (p-value=0.011<0.05); between love/respect behavior and feelings and minor infraction (p-value=0.018<0.05); between love/respect and feelings

Table 6
Significance of the Relationship between the Parent-Child Relationship and Deviant Behavior of Juvenile Children

Parent-Child Relationship	Deviant Behavior of Juvenile Children		
	Minor Infraction	Serious Infraction	Overall
Doing Together	-.529* (0.000)	.374* (0.000)	-.481* (0.000)
Communication/Attention	-.271* (0.000)	-.243* (0.000)	-.274* (0.000)
Helping/Understanding Behavior and Feelings	-.292* (0.000)	-.140* (0.011)	-.231* (0.000)
Love/Respect	.103* (0.018)	-.173* (0.002)	-.161* (0.003)
Conflict	-.100 (0.071)	-.161* (0.003)	-.139* (0.012)
Overall	-.371* (0.000)	-.300* (0.000)	-.358* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

and serious infraction (p-value=0.002<0.05); between conflict and serious infraction (p-value=0.003<0.05).

Overall computation showed an r-value of -.358 while the p-value of 0.000 is lesser when compared with the level of significance of 0.05 indicating significant relationship and the rejection of the null hypothesis. There is therefore a significant relationship between parent-child relationship and deviant behavior of juvenile children.

Mediating Role of Domestic Violence Exposure on the Relationship between Parent-Child Relationship and Deviant Behavior of Juvenile Children

Table 7 shows the regression analysis on the mediating role of domestic violence exposure on the relationship between parent-child relationship and deviant behavior of juvenile children. Medgraph was computed based on the data used as input from the table. There were three steps to be met for a third variable to be acting

Table 7
Mediating Effect: Path Analysis (Partial Mediation)

PATH	ESTIMATES		SE	C.R.	P
	Unstandardized	Standardized			
PCR → DBJC	-.190	-.092	.076	-2.504	.012
PCR → DVE	-.576	-.357	.083	-6.903	***
DVE → DBJC	.947	.744	.047	20.138	***

as a mediator. In Table 7 these were categorized as Steps 1 to 3. In Step 1 (Path c) parent-child relationship as the independent variable (IV) significantly predicted deviant behavior of juvenile children, the dependent variable (DV). In step 2 (Path a) parent child relationship (IV) significantly predicted domestic violence exposure (MV). In step 3 (Path b), domestic violence exposure (MV) significantly predicted deviant behavior of juvenile children (DV). The above-mentioned steps (paths b and c) were significant. The Sobel z-value yielded a p value less than 0.01; hence, significant partial mediation occurred. The association between parent-child relationship (IV) and deviant behavior of juvenile children (DV) had been significantly reduced by the inclusion of the mediating variable which is domestic violence exposure.

Total, Direct, and Indirect Effects

It could be seen in Table 8 that -.7352 was reduced to -.1901 in the subsequent regression. The 95% confidence interval conclusively revealed that significant mediation had occurred. In this particular case, the effect of the IV (parent-child relationship) on DV (deviant behavior of juvenile children) was significantly lessened

Table 8
Total, Direct, and Indirect Effects

Effect	b	95% CI	
		Lower	Upper
Total	-.7352	-.9443	-.5261
Direct	-.1901	-.3398	-.0403
Indirect (mediation)	-.5451	-.7327	-.3607

X = PARENT-CHILD RELATIONSHIP (PCR)
 Y = DEVIANT BEHAVIOR OF JUVENILE CHILDREN (DBJC)

M= DOMESTIC VIOLENCE EXPOSURE (DVE)

after controlling MV (domestic violence exposure). Therefore, only partial mediation took place since the effect was still significant.

The effect size measured how much of the effect of parent-child relationship (IV) on deviant behavior of juvenile children (DV) could be attributed to the indirect path (IV to MV to DV). The total effect (-.7352) was the raw correlation between parent-child relationship (IV) and deviant behavior of juvenile children (DV). The direct effect (-.1901) was the size of the correlation between parent-child relationship (IV) and deviant behavior of juvenile children (DV) with domestic violence exposure (MV) included in the regression. The indirect effect was the amount of the original correlation between the IV and the DV that went through the mediator to the DV ($a*b$) where “a” refers to the path between IV and MV and “b” refers to the path between the MV and the DV. The ratio index was computed by dividing the indirect effect by the total effect, in this case $-.5451$ by $-.7352 = 74.14\%$. It seemed that about 74.14% of the total effect of the IV on the DV went through the MV, and about 25.86% of the total effect was either direct or mediated by other variables not included in the model.

Figure 2. The Mediating Effect of Domestic Violence Exposure on the Relationship between Parent-Child Relationship and Deviant Behavior of Juvenile Children.

The mediating role of domestic violence exposure on the relationship between parent-child relationship and deviant behavior of juvenile children showed partial mediation, wherein 74.14 percent of the total effect of the IV on

the DV went through the MV, and about 25.86 percent of the total effect was either direct or mediated by other variables not included in the model. This shows that three quarters of parent-child relationship passes through domestic violence exposure going through deviant behavior of juvenile children. The result proved the veracity of Travis Hirschi's social bond theory (1969). It is one of the most frequently investigated frameworks for the parent-child relationship and delinquency or deviant behavior. It assumes that delinquent behaviors occur when the individual's bond to family and society is weak or broken.

Proposed Intervention Scheme

Rationale

Deviant Children almost always end up becoming children in conflict with the law and although DSWD exerted effort in rehabilitating them, majority of them will still end up law breakers when they reach adulthood. Sad but true, they seemed to take pride in committing atrocities, which they wanted their peers to see and expect to be praised for the crimes they have done. Their sense of importance is the most important thing for them and they longed to be praised and admired even if it means doing what is illegal (Office of Juvenile Justice and Delinquency Prevention, 2014).

Deviant Children can be attributed to the negligence of parents or cruelty of parents, wherein these children were exposed to domestic violence and parents-child relationship suffered creating a gap in the relationship eventually leading this children to stow-away or runaway and found refuge among their peers whose influence is almost always not good and they celebrate when they defy the law. These are the children that needed intervention and needed to be reconciled to their parents provided their parents are willing to change and bent on raising a family with no violence.

The objectives of this intervention scheme are stated as follows:

1. Compel parents to spend time with their children
2. View things from the child's perspective to understand them
3. Educate parents about little things that are considered wrong by the society and law
4. Filter the things viewed by children online and in the television.

Table 9. Intervention Scheme

Areas of Concern	Activities	Objectives	Personnel Involved	Budget	Date	Expected result
Doing Together	Conduct series of seminar workshops held in an annual Basis by DSWD for parents in every Barangay	To take encourage parents to spend more quality time with their children	Competent DSWD personnel and model parents sharing important subjects on quality time	Appropriation of the seminar workshops Php200/per head times 100 parents/ barangay for one day only comprises of 1 meal and 2 snacks	At the Start of 1 st quarter of the year 2023	Parents will learn the importance of spending quality time with their children
Helping/Understanding Behavior and Feelings		To learn to see from the perspective of the child	Competent Psychologist as speaker on how to see things from the eyes of the child			Parents will fully understand why their children are acting such ways
Minor Infraction Orientation		To orient parents about minor infraction that could destroy the sense of morality of children	Competent Educator who would emphasize the importance of morality			Parents will learn how to teach their children not to commit minor violations
Domestic Violence in TV, Computers and Smart Phones		To control what the children watches and inform them about the danger of watching violent shows	Competent DSWD personnel who will point out the influence of violent show, including domestic violence			Parents will learn to monitor their children when using gadgets and watching television

VIII. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the conclusions are drawn such as the level of parent-child relationship is high. The level of deviant behavior among juvenile children is low as well as their exposure to domestic violence. The Law enforcers should do their part in the information campaign emphasizing RA 9262, wherein the rights of women and children are protected by the law to avoid further damage to the emotional and psychological elements of the children.

Lastly, there is correlation between parent-child relationship and domestic violence exposure; furthermore, there is correlation between domestic violence exposure and deviant behavior of juvenile children; as well as an existing correlation between parent-child relationship and deviant behavior of juvenile children; and, there is partial mediation of domestic violence exposure on the relationship between parent-child relationship and deviant behavior of juvenile children. Parents should be able to know the effect of their bickering inside their homes that affects the children psychologically, and may agree to argue their misunderstanding outside the sight and hearings of the children, as well as controlling the devices that can show domestic violence, particularly television, laptops, and smart phones.

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